

The Effects of Economic Crisis on Libraries and Information Centers in Nigeria

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Abdulsalami T. Lucky PhD-¹Federal University Lafia, PMB 146. University Library, Lafia, Nasarawa State. Nigeria ⁽²⁾Omosigho A. Nsikanabasi Msc-²Federal University Lafia, PMB 146. University Library, Lafia, Nasarawa State. Nigeria

Abstract

Nigeria global economy has experienced a steep crisis that is affecting all sectors of Nigerian society. Nigeria officially entered a recession in May 2015 that made public spending cuts inevitable. Libraries are particularly vulnerable to changes in the world economy because of their reliance on highly-priced globally-sourced information products and dependence on expenditure allocations from parent institutions that are heavily dependent on public funding. An investigation of initial and anticipated effects of the crisis on libraries in Nigeria higher education was examined. Provision and Utilization of information resources and services are particularly indispensable to most Nigerian university students in view of its special importance. The provision of access and use of information resources and services to students is the functional role of the university library to make them independent and efficient in their search for materials to satisfy their information needs. However, the situation becomes worsened due to the economic crisis as a result mismanagement/mal administration or lack of interest of Nigeria leaders towards Library operation. Nigeria is a developing economy where the money for essential services is inadequate. Library development is affected by various economic conditions within the country. This serves the purpose for which the study was investigated, to determine how the economic crisis has affected library and information center development in Nigeria. The study uses documentary sources and observation to investigate its collection of facts.

Keyword: Economic Condition, Information Processing, Production, Economic crisis, Library

Introduction

Economic crisis referred to lack of funds for the effective operations of public organizations and services including library and information service. As observed from media sources in newspapers, magazines, radio, television and seminars and conferences. The most prevailing cry today in the midst of plenty of individuals, families, government and even religious organizations is poverty and lack of funding. Today economic crisis has become a global problem and a national concern in Nigeria.

The most discussions today are tied down on how to overcome economic crisis-a syndrome that is most rendering important sector of the nation's economy handicap. The effects of economic crisis in Nigeria on families and on an individual cannot be overemphasized. There is no doubt the crippling of important projects including library and information service projects nationally. Whereas; library and information centers are the important fabric of the society which shoulder the role of gathering, processing, communicating, transmitting and disseminating information to many information seekers on different subjects. Indeed, no nation whether developed or underdeveloped can assume the function of information gathering, repackaging, storage, processing and disseminating without taking into cognizance the role of libraries and information centers (Mustapha, 2007).

It is well-recognized that library depends heavily upon the financial position of their parent organization and therefore largely reflect the state of that organization (Roberts, 2003). This level of dependence puts the library in a vulnerable position (Hayes and Brown, 2004). The financial environment of libraries has moved towards greater accountability and formalized procedures, partly caused by competing demands for resources (Hayes and Brown, 2004; Roberts, 2003). Library management requires acute knowledge of financial processes, often reflected by budgeting models making an explicit link to objectives, such as the Planning Program Budgeting System (PPBS) McKay, 2003. The literature on library financial management focuses on the theme of instability, with the argument that "change is the only financial constant" (Hayes and Brown, 2004). This is problematic as incremental budget models are based on historical precedent (Linn, 2007). Zero-based budgeting

(ZBB) places less emphasis on precedent, with a notable implementation at Aston University Library (Evans, 2001, McKay, 2003). Defending the value of financial investment in the library is difficult because “libraries lack a definable product or final output” (Roberts, 2003), which is exacerbated by the unique status of information (Kingma, 2001; Feather, 2008). There is continuing growing interest in investigating the value of the library, with several studies developing frameworks for cost analysis (Kingma, 2001; Missingham, 2005).

Economic Conditions and Development of Information Services

The success of any activity in any nation-state rests on a formidable economic and information base. It is in this sense that economic power process by any nation-state determines its active participation in the world affairs.

Nwachukwu, Abdulsalami and Salami (2014) posit that Nigerian economy was based primarily on agriculture and later on raw materials production (oil). The economy becomes weak to guarantee active initiative goals simply because of corruption, sectionalism, religious sentiments, regionalism and what have you while the price of raw materials fluctuated at the international market because they were determined by the advanced capitalist.

The value of information to any society at all times is hardly in doubt, especially its importance to national development. Landau (2003) maintained that information is central to all human activities and it is essential to human survival. It is the lifeblood of any organization. Information is useful in decision making, evaluation of any program and in planning.

Abdulsalami et al (2013) observed that, the library is any activities performed to facilitate any of the stages of the life cycle of any piece of information. The library is home of information that passes through various stages right from the creation stage, to processing, organizing, storage, retrieval, transfer, dissemination, use and exposition. Information services help to transform or to convey information from a specific format, medium, location and or time into another more valuable format, medium, location or time.

Abdulsalami, et al posit that library was created to meet certain social necessities and its development is closely related not only to intellectual history but also to change in the organizational structure and the value system of its supporting culture, should be apparent from even a cursory reading of the record. The library is regarded as an agency of information and information services using information manager (library staff) to manage it.

The library in short is a storehouse of information and according to Ogunsheye (2002) libraries, archives, documentations centers and museums are no longer just repositories of man’s intellectual products, but also centers of generation and creations of findings tools: catalogues, bibliographies, indexes, schedules. They also serve as the center of the collection, analysis, storage, repackaging and dissemination of knowledge and information. Library also provides a base for the application of technologies and methods for creating a critical edge for information services by the information manager.

Penniman (2003) concluded that information delivery system that exists in our society, none is as pivotal as the library because the library is first and foremost a people oriented information delivery. The International Labour Organization (ILO) (1970) estimated that developing countries would need a long-term economic growth rate of 7 to 8 percent per annum, accompanied by sustainable income redistribution policies if they were to meet the basic needs of the poorest people in their societies by the end of the century. (ILO, 1976) in view of such pressing needs and partly also in the light of the generally successful record of the developing countries during the previous two decades the United Nations General Assembly in its December 1980 resolution on the International Development Strategy for the third world nations development decade stated that “the average annual rate of growth of gross domestic product for developing countries as a whole during the decade [of 1980] should be 7 per cent”.

However World Bank (1992) data show the actual experience of 1980’s for a large number of developing countries, particularly in Latin American and Sub-Saharan African has been greatly at variance with this

ambition. In 1965 -1975 the period before the first oil shock, the developing countries as a whole (i.e. the hundred or so low and middle income economies in the World Bank definition managed to achieve a rate of growth of GNP per capita of 4.3 per cent per annum. For the poor majority of the world, this was by any standard a fast rate of materials development as it implied a doubling of per capita GNP every sixteen-seventeen years; it was also in line with the rate required to meet the basic needs of the poorest in these countries by the years 2000.

Through borrowing, third world nations by and large also managed to bear the first oil shock and other fluctuations in the world economy in the 1970s. They were able to achieve an overall rate of growth of GNP per capita of 2.6 percent per annum during 1973 –1980. During 1980-1990, however, this growth rate declined to 1.5 per cent despite the fact that since 1973 the population in developing countries grew at the rate of 2.0 percent per annum. In African and Latin American countries, the 1980s was a disastrous decade: these countries have experienced a sizeable fall in their per capita GNP. Not surprisingly, this decline has been accompanied by a large reduction in real wages and employment in a wide range of countries on the two continents. The World Bank data also point to this important fact: the sharply contrasting experience of the Asian countries in the 1980s relative to those in Africa and Latin America. Notwithstanding the world economic crisis both South and East Asian countries increased their trend rate of GNP per capita in the 1980s; they also achieved significant increases in employment.

In most African countries in general and Nigeria in particular, most crusades through all forms of media today is the trumpet on how to overcome economic crisis syndrome that is almost rendering important sectors of the country economy handicap. The effects of economic crisis globally, nationally on families and on individuals cannot be overemphasized. There is no doubt that economic crisis has not left the information sector. The core of this research is in the information sector of Nigeria economy and especially on libraries and information centers.

Information Production and the Economy

Akerl and his co-winners challenged a fundamental principle of classical economics, the idea that free markets are inherently efficient. They challenged this principle and introduced the idea that the market operates inefficiently if there is an unequal distribution of information about the commodities being traded. Akerl argued that market operate inefficiently if buyer and seller act with imperfect or inadequate information. If a seller has better information about products quality than a buyer so called asymmetric information then a market is likely to collapse entirely or result in an offering of low quality products that causes the market to contract rather than grow. Hence the need to present and verify quality so that buyer and seller shared the same information so that market can operate efficiently.

Information Processing and Economy

Library and information centers are important fabric in any economy also to the information sector or any society. Shera argues that the library as a social instrument takes it shape and purpose from the society and culture in which it is established. Taking the library to be a “social instrument” implies that it is and has been a part of the communication pattern of society, preserving, organizing and disseminating the graphic record of the society as a whole. Librarians shoulder the roles of gathering, selection, processing, communication, transmission and dissemination of information from one place to another or to the intended audience and subjects for the benefit of future generation.

Statement of the Problem

No nation whether developed and less developed or underdeveloped can assume the role of information without taking into cognizance the roles of libraries and information centers. The researchers pick interest in

undertaking the effect of the economic crisis on libraries with the view to identify the problems and making some recommendations on how to overcome such problem.

The economic aspect is characterized by a decrease in activities and public finance. Hence could it be that libraries in Nigeria are functioning as they should due to financial constraints. On social and educational aspect, most Nigerians have a high rate of adults' illiteracy, low rate of primary literacy etc. in terms of collection, selection, processing, dissemination and distribution to the users.

Rodwell described the economy impact on libraries and information service. And posit that all public funding was badly affected by the economic recession in the late 1970s to the present day Nigeria. The public sector, libraries budgets were reduced or retained at existing levels which taking inflation into consideration, constituting an overall reduction in funding services which already adversely affected the library functions, others being trimmed, and expansion in services being in abeyance. These therefore, without any doubt affected the development of libraries and information services in our country.

Effects of Economic Crisis on Library and Information Users

Audu (2008) examine the financial support of the libraries and information centers, listed the financial allocation to them identified that there was a problem of funds, staff, space and non-availability of local publications as a result for which users were aware of their existence.

Audu (2008) discover that economic crisis effects library and information centers and this results to a hindrance in normal weeding of libraries and information centers materials, as preserving and reserving is done only on relevant materials that are necessary for libraries and information centers to functions. And because of the effects of economic crisis many library and information centers cannot afford new materials and thereby turning the role of libraries into archives. Making the libraries and information centers to lose its relevance to its users while the collection development departments in some library and information centers become historical units.

Abdulsalami et al (2013) posit that the consumable that ought to be provided by the government for running the day to day activities becomes standstill. Such consumables are stationeries, duplicating papers, photocopy inks, serials, maintenance of office equipment, etc... there were no funds for the provision of these essential services thereby constituting bottleneck on the library and information centers administration. Abdulsalami summed up by saying that economic crisis syndrome has contributed to magnitude measures in deviating the pragmatic relevant of library and information centers in almost all underdeveloped countries.

Abdulsalami further revealed that infrastructural needs such as transport, communication system, water, light are completely absence in some libraries and information centers for which users are aware of the existence in the libraries and information centers. Beside, money now being voted for books and other information materials is no longer enough to pay for annual journal subscriptions of the various libraries and information centers. The effects of economic crisis on that sector, is in such a gloomy state in that most libraries and information centers cannot possibly achieve some of the basic objectives of the libraries and information centers.

The administration of libraries and information centers has on occasion frozen certain vacant position (resulting from registration of appointments) instead of filling such vacant positions, whereas there are very important services on the libraries and information centers which ought to stay open from morning till evening have to be closed in the evening due to shortage of staff. Suffice, it is necessary to say that no libraries and information centers can be adequately stocked with necessary books, periodicals and provide essential services and facilities unless there is an economic boom.

The importance of seminars, conferences, workshop, public lecturers, symposiums, debates and creating awareness through all forms of medias and what libraries and information centers are, what they provide cannot be overemphasized, but it is disheartening to say that they cannot afford such vital and important programmed

due to the effects of economic crisis syndrome, users' remains under perpetual darkness as the libraries and information centers could no longer provide needed information to their users.

Causes of Non Development of Library and Information Centers

Britz (2004) examine a moral reflection on information poverty in a journal of information science, 30 (3) 2004 said that one of the biggest challenges facing the world today is that of information poverty which if not addressed can cause a negative effect in the economic, cultural and socio-political development of the third world nations. He expresses that information is required for survival and development. He opines that information is related to the basic minimum needs of humanity as well as information tools for trade and economic development. Information must be regarded as a public good, which should be in most cases non exclusionary in nature, the reason being that there is a social benefit from using it. As non-exclusionary it could be funded by means of taxes, donations, non-governmental organization etc.

Assouma (2003) said that the lack of space, fund and qualified staff is the main cause of the underdevelopment of libraries and information centers in Nigeria. She suggested that the Nigeria Library Association (NLA) must have an appropriate place where libraries functions must be done based on the three basic functions which are acquisition, organization and dissemination of information to users who need them for their own interest to develop the economic, cultural and socio-political aspect of life. She concluded by saying that information is the key to power. Information becomes synonymous with power and countries which neglect its development will become inferior to those developed nation which will use it to create a new monopoly.

Bozimo (2008) in her lectures on library automation lamented that it is unfortunate that given the circumstances of most libraries in Africa, that most libraries are not computerized or automated because of our underdevelopment which is the core of the economic crisis, which is one the reason for the non-computerization of libraries and information centers. Moreover, due to the effects of economic crisis libraries and information centers that belong to the academic environment remains perpetually in its exiting manual system operations instead of adoption of the modern computerized system to cope with up to date challenges. Automation in libraries has helped in so many ways such as:

- Increase work load;
- Providing adequate service to the large patrons;
- Greater efficiency in term of time saving speed, accuracy, easy accessibility;
- Newer services
- Cooperative a centralize services etc.

Library computerization is imperative, desirable but not obtainable due to the effects of an economic crisis that is hitting the most of Africa's countries. Abu (2006) on his lecture libraries and information service resources development emphasized that what makes libraries and information centers dynamic and up to date living organism is when enough funds are provided for the libraries. This will enhance, purchase of new materials and weed away outdated materials for libraries and information centers to assume its pragmatic relevance. However, he lamented that due to lack of funds, collection development function could not be carried out in many libraries and information centers as a result library almost become archives and not libraries and information centers. And that, whenever there is an economic crisis, libraries and information centers are also affected/ mostly felt majorly in the areas of collection development unit.

Factors Responsible for Economic Crisis on Libraries and Information Centers

Dowuon (2004) sees the source of economic crisis and its effects on libraries and information centers as general administrative inefficiency. Ractiff (2004) in his visit to some of the libraries and information centers in Nigeria Universities Libraries, advice the government, especially on their finance and administrative practice. During

the visit he discovered that only University of Nigeria Nsukka library was getting the 5% of the University annual total budget as earlier recommended by the government among other things to enhance their efficient running. The most of Nigerian Universities Libraries and Information Centers were not getting the 5% of the annual budget which forms the pivot of the economic crisis that is affecting their performance.

Ogundeko Committee (2008) examined the financial plans arrangements and practices of University libraries and information centers and other institutions financed by government parastatals and other higher institutions of learning according to priority. The rate of funding recommended by the government for the development of the libraries and information centers at 5% of the total recurrent was considered reasonable but that more capital grants need to be provided. The recommendation was made in recognition of the fact that a good library and information center is essential for sound scholarship. But it is unfortunate that studies conducted later and reviewed below did not reflect any improvement that could be attributed to the result of the implementation of the finding of the earlier studies, so all these lacks of implementation of the libraries and information centers today is due to finance causes crises in the world of library and information center.

According to Abdulsalami (2013) examining Kashim Ibrahim Library of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria budget practice and principles discovered that there was no maintenance of acceptable system of accounting that could enhance efficiency in overcoming economic crisis on that sector, the researchers also observed that out of ₦60, 000,000 million budgeted for Federal University Library Lafia for 2012/2013 section, only about ₦15, 000,000- ₦20.000, 000 was expended on the library. From the above review it could be seen that the initial fund made available for running the libraries and information center is either grossly inadequate or not expended especially for the purpose meant for, given the growth of students population tremendous output of publication to choose from and specialized discipline to cater for, leading to economic crisis on libraries and information centers.

Availability of Information Resources for the Development of the Library

The Committee of the Ahmadu Bello University Council (1992) on its recommendation of Kashim Ibrahim Library stated that inability to pay special regards to libraries and information centers despite the information resources provided to facilitate learning and research is a factor for its economic crisis. Ractiff (2004) gave a summary of the outcome of the visit to Nigeria libraries and information centers, in universities, government parastatals and other high institutions of learning. The aim of the visit was to see the practice of western libraries, their methods and techniques. He discovered that there was a problem of finance that constitutes a bottle neck on institutions. Not only that he was able to discover also that there was a problem of trained personnel or professional that runs the day-to-day activities and their central duty and functions. He said there was a need for the government to consider its expenditure so that they will be able to support their libraries and information centers in universities and other higher institutions of learning. Moreover he discovered that considerable staffing and technical development was restricted due to the inadequacy of trained personnel.

Haruna (2006) in his lecture “serial management in libraries and information centers” stressed that there are so many problems of discontinuity in serials department because of problems of ordering of serial that trend to be chaotic. Moreover he highlighted that standardization and automation is needed in the libraries, the need to standardize and a compelling shift towards automation as a welcome idea. Problems of libraries emanate as a result of economic crisis when a financial stand of most libraries and information centers are uncomfortable. Given also the underdeveloped countries circumstances, most of the materials use for publishing serials nowadays are non-quality materials, they are not durable, they are inferior and the importance of quality in any product cannot be overemphasized. But it is unfortunate that the effects of the economic crisis have compelled some publishers into using inferior materials which in turn equally affects libraries and information centers collections in order to meet it users demand due to the effects of economic crisis. There is a professional journal that is being subscribed from abroad, these journals incur a high cost due to currency value differences,

these journals cannot be afforded again as it was during oil boom period, prior to the effects of economic crisis on libraries and information centers.

Musa (2006) in his lecture on information technology said that: given Nigeria circumstances in which we are blessed with natural resources that would have to enhance rapid growth and development especially in the area of information technology. He emphasizes corruption, mismanagement and all forms of evil vices that bar the pragmatic relevance of information technology especially on libraries and information centers. He suggested that if Africans in general and Nigeria in particular could manage their resources judiciously the use of Wide Areas Network (WAN) lacking in libraries and information centers compared to advance economy would not be a problem. That Local Areas Network could also be used to enhance libraries and information centers cooperation and resources sharing to enhance growth and development. But he lamented that it is unfortunate that corruption, poor administration, political interference and inability and all forms of evil vices has paralyzed the pragmatic relevant and the function of information technology on libraries and information centers which are products of economic crisis. He stressed that if there were the implementation of information technology in libraries and information centers better services, efficiency and accuracy would be the end result. “It is desirable but not obtainable” as economic crisis syndrome has almost affected every sector of the economy.

Economic downturns can detrimentally affect the collections budgets that library maintain and develop. There is ample evidence of reduced collection budgets in public and university library in the United Kingdom, United State American and Nigeria across different economic downturns (Roden, 2001). Recent surveys give further evidence that budgets in general and book budgets in particular decrease in poor economic conditions. Detailed anecdotal articles document effects collections: the University of Ottawa leased out its holdings in 1988 (Kwong, 2003), whilst the collection at the University of Ibadan became inadequate for supporting research (Ekpenyong, 2003). Valuable research in Canada and the UK have found incremental but steady declines in collection quality in periods of economic contraction.

Adverse effects on library collections can cause a cultural shift to enterprise risk management, with services relying on diversified funding (Hoffert, 2009) university libraries in Africa have relied on donations and supplementary charges to cope with lack of resources (Kanyengo, 2009), reinforcing the argument that reduced resources provide an opportunity to review programs and to develop new ways to meet objectives (Prentice, 2003). Positive marketing in reaction to such circumstances is a key feature of library responses to economic crises (Rooney-Browne, 2009). Some literature links enterprise to managerial competencies and dynamism (Evans, 2001) Financial constraint can be a catalyst for radical changes, with the opportunity to make constructive improvements to organizational structure (Brindley, 2001). A further effect on collection management can be more resource sharing, with ICOLC (2009) suggesting that consortia purchasing may increase as a result of the downturn. Collaborative collections have been widely viewed as beneficial for academic library enhancing purchasing power and improving service to users (Follett, 2008). Line (2006) recognises that an academic library can never have a comprehensive collection, but points out the cost of unnecessary co-operative practice. Human Resources in the library are acknowledged as labour-intensive organizational units in which the largest single expenditure is typically staff, making that a major target for cuts (McKay, 2003). The vulnerability of human resources in library contrasts with the notion that a workforce is an asset that appreciates in value over time (White, 2007). A common effect of poor economic conditions is a reduction in staffing spend. Statistics collated by Davis (2009) suggest that fewer library professionals are employed during economic downturns.

Availability of Human Resources for the Development of the Library

The Business Information Survey found that 75% of managers had lost or expected to lose staff (Foster, 2009). In contrast, some data show that library staff expenditure remains stable in downturns, with the special library sector suffering most (Griffiths et al., 2009). Published evidence suggests that universities in the USA and UK are likely to make cuts in the current crisis (Dalton, 2009; Times Higher Education, 2009), conforming to a pattern of evidence documenting staff cuts in both the USA and UK in recent and previous downturns

(American Libraries, 2003; Brook, 2008). This can negatively impact staff-student ratios (Kwong, 2003). As a natural adjunct of job cuts, recruitment is often reduced in a downturn, with Evans (2001) suggesting that leaving vacant positions unfilled is less damaging for academic libraries than implementing redundancies. Tomer (2002) presents evidence of this at the corrected final draft, December 2010 New Review of Academic Librarianship, 17 (1) 5 universities of Minnesota and Pittsburgh.

A further effect can be more flexible staffing hours and more fixed-term contracts (Hill, 2002). Davis (2009) suggests that salary levels in the library profession remain stable in economic downturns. Goulding's (2000) study identified blurring of boundaries between Para-professional and professional job responsibilities in this context. Partly due to their high cost, staff - represent a "prime material to develop." The conjunction of increased use with service contraction has resulted in the idea that during recessions, libraries are fortunate to simply maintain services, yet, paradoxically; the demand for their services grows (Evans et al., 2000). Service portfolios often suffer as a result of economic difficulties, as it can be an easy way to reduce costs (Line, 2006). Portfolios are contracting at present, with closures and reduced hours in progress in the US and UK (Library and Information Update, Roberts, 2009; Topper, 2009) identifies the problem of an "information recession" with library unable to fund high-quality information technology (IT) facilities. IT and other technological equipment have high maintenance costs, requiring constant capital for up-keep and replacement (Tebbetts, 2000). A tough economic climate can cause streamlining of services, eliminating unnecessary procedures and reducing costs (Kennard, 2008). Evidence suggests that downturns lead to concentration on the delivery of core services, which can lead to a realignment of priorities (Topper, 2009).

Solutions to Overcome Economic Crisis in Libraries and Information Centers

Adeeiza (2002) examined the criteria of providing funds for libraries and information centers owned by governments as the main source of the economic crisis on libraries and information centers. He therefore suggested on improvement in the accounting system in order to overcome economic crisis affecting libraries and information centers functions. Swanson (2004) while studying the administration and organization of libraries and information centers observed that the function of acquiring libraries and information centers resources is highly professionalized. Librarians should endeavor to search for the appropriate materials available in the market as well as connecting/liaising with the faculties/departments for the purchase of specific materials. He proposed a professionalized acquisition unit to be established in each library and information centers, acquisition to save personal and unnecessary expenses.

Ocheibi (2006) examined the economic crisis faced by libraries and information centers as not only the problems emanating from low grant and allocation of funds from the government only. But that the other support that the libraries would have gotten from non-governmental bodies to overcome economic crisis are not made available since those bodies are also facing economic imbalance. He concluded by saying that in the libraries and information centers, grants are grossly inadequate and that there was too much imbalance between the expenditure of the stock and salaries hence the crisis. Highan (2006) identified the reason for the economic crisis in libraries and information centers especially in acquisition unit as a result of lack of economic management of the available funds and resources availability. And suggested that economic measure is brought in which will help to maintain the system. He stressed areas that are important such as the purchasing unit and staffing. And that library is a special and vulnerable organ of academic institutions and that unless it is protected and maintain intact in times of stress the institutions will never recover. He suggested that personnel that should be involved in the acquisition unit of the librarian must have fund knowledge of the economic environment in order to be able to determine the option out of various alternatives. As to save cost and maintain the flow and the needs of this vital sector of learning institutions.

Easton (2002) identified some of the problems that resulted in libraries and information centers being jeopardized by the economic crisis as lack of employment and other means of raising funds for running libraries. He suggested that launching an appeal fund for libraries and information centers can go a long way in solving most of the economic crisis faced by the libraries and information centers. On fund raising for libraries

and information centers he gave detail of basic information needed and the kinds of approaches available for successful fund raising. He stated that needs of libraries and information centers were diverse and the needs could be packaged in numerous and convincing ways as to attract donation to overcome the problem of the economic crisis on libraries and information centers through fund raising.

Wilson (2002) lamented that austerity had caught the libraries and information centers in their number where success, progress, and academic achievement are measured by comparing statistic of operation. And that the exercise which shows only largest number does not show quality and the large number cannot often be equated with effectiveness. He felt that comprehensiveness is not although ever the answer but effective resources sharing, for even with investment libraries and information centers cannot keep up with estimated percentage annual growth rate in the world's output of publication and that the annual percentage of books vote cannot offset inflation accessibility to other libraries and information centers collections, extensive photocopying, libraries and information centers network, effective national bibliographic system are some of this suggestion. The effect of the economic crisis on libraries and information centers is a concern of library administrators.

Conclusion

Economic crisis profound effects on library and information center. Nigeria is a developing economy where the money for essential services is inadequate. Library development is affected by various economic conditions within the country. This serves the purpose for which the study was investigated, to determine how the economic crisis has affected library and information center development in Nigeria. The study uses documentary sources and observation to investigate its collection of facts. Various lecturers' opinions and note were a sample. And it was discovered that people are highly dependent on library and information center, students, lecturers, researchers etc. are the most important users of library and information center. Most library and information center are not computerized while clientele is not satisfied as enough funds are not made available for library and information center operation. Libraries thus face numerous effects of economic conditions, which vary across organizations and types of operation.

Recommendation

1. Library and information center should generate funds for their own running of their library instead of depending solely on parent body or government.
2. The poor economic management system by Librarians in the academic library should be revitalized
3. Funds rising means should be device by most libraries to overcome the dependency
4. The library and information center should automate their collections and personnel training should be encouraged, enhancing staff and technical development in library and information centers for better service delivery.
5. Librarians/Library administrators should wake up in their sleeping and slumber if they want to remain relevant in their profession as a result of information explosion of the new century.

References

- i. Abu Y. (2006) *Lecture Note on information Resources development. Ahmadu Bello University, a. Department of Library and Information Science. Zaria. Kaduna State.*
- ii. Abdulsalami T. Lucky and Paulina F. Salami and Tawal D. Sale. (2013) *Information sourcing and Use among small and Medium enterprises (SME) in Kogi State, Nigeria for knowledge society. African Library Sentinel (ALS). Journal for Library and Information Science (JLIS) UNN Nsukka 2(2) 18*
- iii. Adeiza, M. (2009) *An Evaluation of impact of common European Project currency (Euro) on a. International Business. Thesis MBA Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.*

- iv. *Analysis for Information Professionals, 2001. 2nd ed. Colorado: Libraries Unlimited.*
- v. *Audu I. S. (2008) The Libraries appeal for more fund for the Library Launching. (Zaria a. ABU):27.*
- vi. *Bozimo, O. (2008) Note on the Introduction to Digital information System and Services.*
- vii. *Brindley, C.B. (2001) The library in hard times, Library Journal. December, 981-987.*
- viii. *Britz, J. J. (2004) To know or not to know: A Moral Reflection on Information Poverty: Journal a. of information science, 30(3)193.*
- ix. *Brook, M.D. (2008) Library leadership in times of crisis and change. New Library World, 106 a. (1216-1217), 395-415.*
- x. *Convergence – Libraries of the Future, 2008. pp. 55-64. London: Springer.*
- xi. *Dalton, R. (2009) Public universities left reeling by recession. Nature [Online], 458, 14-15. a. <http://www.nature.com/news/2009/090304/full/458014a.html> [Accessed 15 November b. 2010]*
- xii. *Davis, H. (2009) A look at recessions and their impact on librarianship, In the Library with the a. Lead Pipe, 14 January. <http://www.inthelibrarywiththeleadpipe.org/2009/a-look-at-recessions-and-their-impact-on-librarianship/> [Accessed 15 November 2010]*
- xiii. *Ekpenyong, G.D. (2003) The economic recession on university libraries: the case of Kenneth a. Dike Library. New Library World, 9 (1107), 19-22.*
- xiv. *Easton A. (2002) Fund Raising for Universities Libraries and College Research Libraries. xv. 32 (5) 251 – 361*
- xvi. *Evans, G.E. (2001) The in's and out of library budget preparation, The Bottom Line: Managing a. Library Finances. 14 (1), 19-23.*
- xvii. *Feather, J. (2008) The Information Society: A Study of Continuity and Change. 5th ed. London: a. Facet.*
- xviii. *Follett, B.K. () World-class universities need world-class libraries and information resources: a. but how can they be provided? in: Earnshaw, R. and Vince, J. (eds), Digital*
- xix. *Foster, A. (2009) Battening down the hatches: the business information survey. Business a. Information Review, 26 (1), 10-27.*
- xx. *Goulding, A. (2000) An Examination of the Effects of the Economic Climate on All Levels a. of Personnel within a Library Service. Masters Dissertation, University of Sheffield.*
- xxi. *Hayes, S. and Brown, D. (2004) The library as a business: mapping the pervasiveness of a. financial relationships in today's library, Library Trends. 42 (3), 404-419.*

- xxii. Haruna, M. (2006) *Lecture Note on information Resources development. Ahmadu Bello a. University, Department of Library and Information Science. Zaria. Kaduna State.*
- xxiii. Highan, J. A. N. (2006) “Priority service in stress situation, proceeding at a national a. conference at sear borough 6 – 9th September.
- xxiv. Hoffert, B. (2009) *It’s the economy, Library Journal. 134 (3), 34-36.*
- xxv. ILO (International Labor Office). (1976) *Employment, Growth and Basic Needs: A one World a. Problem Geneva ILO. Economically Active Population: 1950-2025. Vol 5. Geneva ILO.*
- xxvi. Kanyengo, C.W. (2009) *Meeting collection development needs in resource poor settings: the a. University of Zambia Medical Library experience. Collection Building, 28 (1), 26-30.*
- xxvii. Kennard, D. (2008) *Library management in times of economic constraint: the polytechnic a. library, Library Management in Times of Economic Constraints: Papers read at a One b. Day Seminar organized by the School of Librarianship and Information Studies, May, c. pp. 9-14. Liverpool: Liverpool Polytechnic.*
- xxviii. Kwong, J. (2003) *Canadian universities in an age of austerity: moving towards the business a. model, Oxford Review of Education. 19 (1), 65-77.*
- xxix. Landau, C.M. and Mbewe, G. (2003) *Factors Restraining the formulation and implementation of xxx. National Information Policy (NIP) Process: The Zambian Experiences, African Journal of xxxi. Library, Archival and Information Science 3(1) 3.*
- xxxii. Line, M. (2006) *The survival of academic libraries in hard times: reactions to pressures, a. rational and irrational. British Journal of Academic Librarianship, 1 (1), 1-12.*
- xxxiii. Linn, M. (2007) *Budget systems used in allocating resources to libraries, The Bottom Line: a. Managing Library Finances. 20 (1), 20-29*
- xxxiv. Mahamadou, A. (2003) *Report on Industrial Attachment to the Ministry of Basic Education.*
- xxxv. McKay, D. (2003) *Effective Financial Planning for Library and Information Services. 2nd a. ed. London: Europa Publications.*
- xxxvi. Musa, G. J. (2006) ‘*Library experience and librarian employment during three recessions*’. a. *Unpublished report for Institute of Museum and Library Services.*
- xxxvii. Mustapha, A. M.(2007) *Economic down tone on Libraries and Information Center: A Case a. Study of the Ministry of Basic Education in Niger Republic.*
- xxxviii. Mussingham, R. (2005) *Libraries and economic value: a review of recent studies, Performance a. Measurement and Metrics. 6 (3), 142-158.*
- xxxix. Nwachukwu, V.N, Abdulsalami, T. Lucky and Paulina F. Salami. (2014) *Information Needs of*

- a. *Marketers of Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. An Empirical Studies. International Organization for Scientific Research. (IOSR)*
- xl. *Ocheibi, J. A. Financing a University with Particular references to ABU Libraries (BLS)*
a. *Thesis Zaria ABU.*
- xli. *Ogundeko Committee on University Finance National Universities Commission*
a. (2008). *Bulletin (Lagos NUC. 64.*
- xlii. *Ogunsheye, F. A. (2002) Prospect for knowledge and Information Transfer Manager in Nigeria*
a. *in the New Millennium (In) Education this Millennium: Innovation in Theoretical and*
b. *Practice.*
- xliii. *Penniman, W.D. (2003) Shaping the Future for library through Leadership and Researches.*
a. *Libraries and the future. Essays on the Library in the Twenty-first Century New York:*
b. *the Haworth Press. 15.*
- xliv. *Prentice, A.E. Financial Planning for Libraries. London: Scarecrow. 2003.*
- xlv. *Ractcliff. W. F. (2004) Western Ways and Nigerian Means: University Librarianship. African*
a. *Research and Document (8ed). 29 – 34.*
- xlvi. *Robert, D. (2003) “Austerity, technology and Resource Sharing: Research Librarian faced the*
a. *future. Library journal. 100(10): 917 – 923.*
- xlvii. *Robertson, G. (2009) Surviving hard times: how libraries can deal with recessions,*
a. *Feliciter, 54 (6), 272-274.*
- xlviii. *Roden, R. A. (2011) Perfect storm in public funding for Florida libraries. Florida Libraries, 52*
a. (1), 8-10.
- xlix. *Rooney-Browne, C. (2009) Rising to the challenge: a look at the role of public libraries in times*
a. *of recession, Library Review. 58 (5), 341-352.*
- l. *Swanson, B and Furtado, E. The Administration Organization of ABU: Report of the Consultant*
a. (By the) *Lagos Field Office of the Food Foundation. 2004*
- li. *Tebbetts, D.R. (2000)The costs of information technology and the electronic library. The*
a. *Electronic Library, 18 (2), 127-136.*
- lii. *The committee of the Ahmadu Bello University Council (1972): National Universities*
a. *Commission Bulletin (Lagos NUC). 70.*
- liii. *Tomer, C. (2002) ‘The effects of the recession on academic and public libraries’, in: Barr, C.*
a. (ed.), *Bowker Annual Library and Trade Almanac. pp. 74-84. New Providence NJ: Bowker.*
- liv. *Topper, E.F. (2009) ‘Tough economic times for US libraries’, New Library World, 110 (5-6),*
a. *291-293. UN. United Nations, World Economic Situation and Prospects 2009. New York: UN.*
<http://www.un.org/esa/policy/wesp/wesp2009files/wesp2009.pdf> [Accessed 15 November 2010]

- lv. White, L N. (2007) *Imperfect reflections: the challenges in implementing human capital assessment in libraries. The Bottom Line: Managing Library Finances*, 20 (4), 141-147.
- lvi. .
- lvii. World Bank (1976) *World development Report*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- lviii. Wilson, A. (2002) *Library Services in time of Recession. IFLA Journal* 9(1)11 – 19.